

Appendix E - Empathy Test Results

We administered the Questionnaire of Cognitive and Affective Empathy (QCAE), a well-established and psychometrically validated instrument, as part of the pre-interview procedure. This appendix presents participants' responses to the empathy test.

QCAE Empathy Scale:

#	Item
1	I sometimes find it difficult to see things from the "other guy's" point of view.
2	I am usually objective when I watch a film or play, and I don't often get completely caught up in it.
3	I try to look at everybody's side of a disagreement before I make a decision.
4	I sometimes try to understand my friends better by imagining how things look from their perspective.
5	When I am upset at someone, I usually try to "put myself in his shoes" for a while.
6	Before criticising somebody, I try to imagine how I would feel if I was in their place.
7	I often get emotionally involved with my friends' problems.
8	I am inclined to get nervous when others around me seem to be nervous.
9	People I am with have a strong influence on my mood.
10	It affects me very much when one of my friends seems upset.
11	I often get deeply involved with the feelings of a character in a film, play, or novel.
12	I get very upset when I see someone cry.
13	I am happy when I am with a cheerful group and sad when the others are glum.

14	It worries me when others are worrying and panicky.
15	I can easily tell if someone else wants to enter a conversation.
16	I can pick up quickly if someone says one thing but means another.
17	It is hard for me to see why some things upset people so much.
18	I find it easy to put myself in somebody else's shoes.
19	I am good at predicting how someone will feel.
20	I am quick to spot when someone in a group is feeling awkward or uncomfortable.
21	Other people tell me I am good at understanding how they are feeling and what they are thinking.
22	I can easily tell if someone else is interested or bored with what I am saying.
23	Friends talk to me about their problems as they say that I am very understanding.
24	I can sense if I am intruding, even if the other person does not tell me.
25	I can easily work out what another person might want to talk about.
26	I can tell if someone is masking their true emotion.
27	I am good at predicting what someone will do.
28	I can usually appreciate the other person's viewpoint, even if I do not agree with it.
29	I usually stay emotionally detached when watching a film.
30	I always try to consider the other fellow's feelings before I do something.
31	Before I do something I try to consider how my friends will react to it.

P19	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Strongly Agree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Slightly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Strongly Disagree										
P20	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Agree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Slightly Disagree																
P21	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Agree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Agree	Slightly Agree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Slightly Disagree												
P22	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Strongly Agree	Slightly Agree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Slightly Disagree	

Empathy Score Calculation:

	Perspective Taking Score	Online Simulation Score	Cognitive Empathy Score	Emotional Contagion Score	Proximal Responsivity Score	Peripheral Responsivity Score	Affective Empathy score	Total Score
P1	34	32	66	9	11	7	27	93
P2	34	32	66	11	14	14	39	105
P3	33	39	72	14	16	15	45	117
P4	32	33	65	9	14	10	33	98
P5	34	32	66	12	15	15	42	108
P6	27	29	56	8	10	8	26	82
P7	23	30	53	11	11	9	31	84

P8	23	22	45	15	16	13	44	89
P9	27	26	53	14	14	12	40	93
P10	26	28	54	4	8	7	19	73
P11	33	33	66	8	7	9	24	90
P12	33	27	60	11	8	12	31	91
P13	32	31	63	14	14	14	42	105
P14	32	36	68	10	11	12	33	101
P15	29	33	62	6	9	12	27	89
P16	34	39	73	11	12	13	36	109
P17	29	32	61	11	12	10	33	94
P18	28	38	66	11	12	12	35	101
P19	24	36	60	6	9	11	26	86
P20	24	23	47	9	10	9	28	75
P21	28	36	64	14	15	12	41	105
P22	34	34	68	8	13	10	31	99

- **Cognitive Empathy Score:** Calculated as the sum of the Perspective Taking Score and the Online Simulation Score.
- **Affective Empathy Score:** Calculated as the sum of the Emotional Contagion Score, Proximal Responsivity Score, and Peripheral Responsivity Score.
- **Total Empathy Score:** Calculated as the sum of the Cognitive Empathy Score and the Affective Empathy Score.